

Prevalence of Human Immunodeficiency Virus and Selected Sexually Transmitted Infections among Female Sex Workers in Jos, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Sexually transmitted infections (STIs), including Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), continue to pose major global public health challenges, especially in sub-Saharan Africa where the burden is disproportionately high. Female sex workers (FSWs) are particularly vulnerable to acquiring and transmitting HIV and other STIs due to high rates of unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners, limited access to healthcare, and marginalization. This study assessed the prevalence of HIV and other STIs, and identified factors associated with HIV infection among FSWs in Jos, Nigeria.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among FSWs in Jos between September and December 2020. Prevalence estimates and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated for HIV and other STIs. Logistic regression was used to determine factors associated with HIV infection.

Results: A total of 175 FSWs were enrolled, with a mean age of 29.5 (± 6.4) years. HIV prevalence was 22.3% (95% CI: 16.7–29.1). *Ureaplasma parvum* was the most prevalent STI (55.4%), followed by *Ureaplasma urealyticum* (50.9%). Prevalence of *Neisseria gonorrhoea*, *Trichomonas vaginalis*, and *Chlamydia trachomatis* was 19.4%, 17.7%, and 12.0%, respectively. Risk factors for HIV included alcohol use (OR 1.2), substance abuse (OR 1.9), known paying partner (OR 1.9), early sexual debut (<18 years, OR 1.1), and *Trichomonas vaginalis* infection (OR 1.0). Consistent condom use was associated with lower odds of HIV infection (OR 0.7).

Conclusion: FSWs in Jos exhibited high HIV and STI prevalence. Interventions such as targeted screening, treatment, substance use reduction, and condom promotion are essential to reduce infection risks in this key population.

Key words: HIV, STI, Brothel based sex workers.

Introduction

Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) are a significant public health challenge, with over 1 million new infections occurring daily worldwide and 376 million new cases of the four curable bacterial STIs reported annually.¹ This reproductive health problem is especially critical in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), which bear the highest burden of STI-related morbidity and mortality.² Nigeria has the second-largest number of HIV infections globally, and one of the highest rates of new infections in sub-Saharan Africa.³ Unprotected sex accounts for 80% of new HIV infections, with a significant portion occurring in key populations such as sex workers.^{4,5} In Nigeria, sex workers make up 3.4% of the population but are responsible for 14.4% of new HIV infections, with an HIV prevalence among sex workers being eight times higher than in the general population.^{6,7} Brothel-based sex workers (BBFSW) are at even greater risk, with a prevalence of 27.4%.^{8,9}

Sex workers not only face a high risk of contracting HIV and other STIs, but also act as reservoirs, bridging these infections to the broader population.^{10,11} Although the global HIV burden has declined with the effective use of antiretroviral therapy (ART), the incidence of other STIs continues to rise, largely due to inconsistent and incorrect condom use and other behavioural factors. It is important to note that while ART reduces HIV transmission, it does not protect against other STIs.^{12,13} This trend is particularly concerning in settings like Jos, Nigeria, where data on this important reproductive health problem is lacking. In LMICs, delayed or inadequate diagnosis and treatment of STIs often result in severe complications, including pelvic inflammatory disease, ectopic pregnancy, chronic pelvic pain, adverse pregnancy outcomes (such as abortion, intrauterine fetal death, and premature delivery), neonatal and infant infections, infertility, genital malignancies, and increased HIV transmission.¹⁴⁻¹⁶

Despite a global decline in the prevalence of HIV and STIs, certain populations, particularly sex workers, continue to be at increased risk and

transmit infections.¹⁶ This high risk population facilitates the transmission of HIV and STIs to their partners and clients, acting as a bridge to the general population.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ This situation is exacerbated by the low rate of condom use, especially with boyfriends or steady partners, reported at 10.5% in previous studies.^{20,21} Furthermore, conventional methods for diagnosing STIs are often insensitive, partly due to the frequent misuse of antibiotics.²²

Many STIs are asymptomatic, and co-infections are common. The misuse of antibiotics in LMICs suppresses the growth of these infections, making diagnosis by conventional methods challenging.²³ Therefore, there is a need for more sensitive techniques that can simultaneously detect multiple pathogens from a single sample for early detection and treatment. This study employed the multiplex polymerase chain reaction (PCR), an advanced molecular biology technique that allows for the simultaneous detection of multiple pathogens from the same sample, to determine the prevalence of HIV and other STIs among female sex workers in Jos.

Methodology

Study design and setting

This was a cross-sectional study conducted in Jos metropolis consisting of parts of Jos North and Jos South Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Plateau State, Nigeria. Plateau State is the twelfth largest state in Nigeria, with an estimated population of 4.7 million. Located in the heart of the country, it stands out geographically with its distinctive elevated hills encircling the Jos Plateau. Jos metropolis, being the main commercial area of Plateau State was chosen for the study because it has well-organized brothel-based commercial sex work in the country.

Study Population and sampling

The study was conducted among female sex workers in Jos metropolis and a female sex worker was defined as a woman who received money or gifts in exchange for sex. The inclusion criteria for the study were being a female sex worker between the ages of 18 to 65 years, stayed in the brothels and

lived within the Jos metropolis with ability to provide informed consent.

Sample size was determined using a single proportion formula with a 95% confidence interval and a prevalence of HIV of 15.5% from a study done on HIV epidemic among key populations in Nigeria.²⁴ A sample size of 201 was arrived at but in view of the fact that the estimated population of female sex workers was less than 10,000, correction for finite population was applied using the appropriate formula²⁵ giving a minimum sample size of 172 female sex workers. A census of all brothels within the metropolis showed that there were 20 brothels in the area. Each of the 20 brothels served as a cluster. Ten brothels (clusters) were then selected using simple random sampling by balloting to provide adequate representation of all the brothels. In each of the 10 brothels selected, all consenting participants were selected. Participants were given an equivalent of 3USD and condoms as compensation for their time.

Data collection and laboratory diagnostics

Data were collected between September to December 2020. An interviewer-administered questionnaire was used to obtain information on sociodemographic characteristics as well as sexual and reproductive history of the participants. The questionnaire was adapted from previous studies. A female gynecologist performed a detailed examination along with a pelvic examination to collect an endocervical sample using a Digene HC2 DNA Collection Device (QIAGEN, CA, USA) and samples were transported from the collection point on dry ice and stored at -80°C until ready for analysis.

Venous blood sample was collected and screened for HIV-1 and HIV-2 using the WHO serial test algorithm. The HIV test was performed using the Alere Determine HIV 1/2 Ag/Ab combo test to detect both HIV1/2 antibodies. Reactive specimens were tested using a third strip by Trinity Biotech Unigold Recombigen HIV test. All participants who tested positive were referred for HIV treatment, care and support.

DNA extraction and molecular detection of STIs

DNA was extracted from the samples using the QIAamp DNA Mini kit (QIAGEN, CA, USA), according to the manufacturer's instructions. After extraction, DNA was concentrated in 100 µL of the elution buffer provided in the extraction kit and stored at -80°C before STI DNA detection. Six bacteria (*Neisseria gonorrhoea*, *Chlamydia trachomatis*, *Mycoplasma genitalium*, *Mycoplasma hominis*, *Ureaplasma parvum* and *Ureaplasma urealyticum*) and one protozoan parasite (*Trichomonas vaginalis*) were detected by molecular biology techniques using the CE IVD-marked multiplex real-time Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) Allplex™ STI Essential Assay (Seegene, Seoul, South Korea, distributed in France by Eurobio Laboratories, Courtaboeuf, France). The kit contained specific primers targeting each of the seven microorganisms' DNA and was based on Seegene's proprietary DPO™ and MuDT™ technologies, which avoided mismatch priming and quantified each target in a single fluorescence channel, respectively. The multiplex PCR reaction was carried out on the CFX96™ real-time PCR instrument (Bio-Rad, Marnes-la-Coquette, France) using 5 µl of swab-extracted DNA and 15 µl of PCR mix. The test was applied to all samples according to the manufacturer's recommendations.

Data management and analysis

Data obtained from the interview and the results of the laboratory tests were entered into Redcap and exported into SPSS version 26 and STATA SE for data analysis. Descriptive statistics were performed using mean with standard deviation (SD) for normally distributed data and median with interquartile range (IQR) for skewed data along with associated 95% confidence interval (CI). The prevalence of each STI was presented as proportion with a 95% CI. Student t-test was used as test of significance for continuous variables and chi square was used to determine the association between categorical variables. Binary logistic regression was used to determine the strength of association between HIV and other variables that were presented as unadjusted odds ratio with 95%

CI. The dependent variable was the HIV status, the independent variables included each of the other STIs, age at coitarche, number of sex partners, consistent and correct condom use at all times, parity, substance abuse and alcohol use.

Ethical clearance and informed consent

The study was approved by the Health Research Ethics Committee of Jos University Teaching Hospital (JUTH/DCS/IREC/127/XXX/2153). Permission was obtained from Brothel owners and leaders in the brothels. Written Informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to data collection. Information concerning study objectives, voluntary participation and confidentiality assurance were provided to all the participants prior to their signing the consent form.

Results

Sociodemographic characteristics

A total of 175 BBFSW were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 29.5(±6.4) years. Fourteen (8.0%) of the 175 participants were unable to read or write. Almost half of them, 65 (48.6%) were single, while 9 (5.1%) were married. Majority of them, 140 (80.0%) reported being previously treated for a sexually transmitted infection. A third of the participants, 65 (37.1%) smoked cigarettes, while 28 (16%) ingested other substances (Table 1). Majority (169; 96.6%) of the women were multiparous and had had at least one abortion. About two-thirds (115; 65.7%) had their first sexual intercourse before the age of 18, and greater than half (105; 60.0%) had between one to five sex partners per day. Another 10 (5.7%) had more than 10 sex partners per day. Greater than half of the participants (109; 62.3%) reported inconsistent condom use and 114 (65.1%) reported having a nonpaying client (Table 2).

HIV and STI Prevalence

As shown in table 3, the prevalence of HIV was 22.3% (95% CI: 16.7-29.1). The proportion of BBFSW who had at least one STI from the study apart from HIV was 157 (89.7%). *Ureaplasma Parvum* was the most prevalent STI at 55.4% (95% CI: 51.2-60.3) followed by *Ureaplasma urealyticum* 50.9% (95% CI: 42.3-57.1). The prevalence of *Neisseria gonorrhoea*, *Chlamydia*

trachomatis and *Trichomonas vaginalis* was 19.4% (95% CI:15.5-24.8), 12.0% (95% CI:10.1-15.9) and 17.7% (95% CI:11.7-22.8) respectively.

Predictors of HIV infection

Predictors of having HIV infection are presented in Table 4. Women who used alcohol (OR 1.2; 95% CI: 0.6-1.9), had history of substance abuse (OR 1.9; 95% CI: 0.6-5.8), had a known paying partner (OR 1.9; 95% CI: 0.5-2.3), had first intercourse at age less than 18 years (OR 1.1; 95% CI: 0.5-2.3), and had infection with *trichomonas vaginalis* (OR 1.0; 95% CI: 0.4-2.6) had increased odds of having HIV infection although these associations were not statistically significant. Participants who reported consistent and correct use of condoms were found to have lower odds of having HIV infection (OR 0.7; 95% CI: 0.4-1.5). However, this was also not statistically significant.

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of study participants

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age group (years)		
<25	48	27.4
25-35	96	54.9
36-45	28	16.0
>45	3	1.7
Level of education		
None	14	8.0
Primary	44	25.1
Secondary	101	57.7
Tertiary	16	9.2
Marital Status		
Divorced	10	5.7
Married	9	5.1
Single	85	48.6
Separated	45	25.7
Widowed	26	14.9
Previous STI treatment		
No	35	20.0
Yes	140	80.0
Smoking status		
No	110	62.9
Yes	65	37.1
Alcohol		
No	67	38.3
Yes	108	61.7
Other Substances		
No	147	84.0
Yes	28	16.0

Table 2: Reproductive characteristics and risk factors for HIV and other Sexually Transmitted Infections among female sex workers in Jos, Nigeria

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Parity		
0-4	169	96.6
≥5	6	3.4
Abortion group		
0	63	36.0
≥1	112	64.0
Age at first coitus		
<18	115	65.7
≥18	60	34.3
Number of Partners /day		
1-5	105	60.0
6-10	60	34.3
>10	10	5.7
Any history of anal sex		
No	154	88.0
Yes	21	12.0
Previous pap smear		
Never	171	97.7
Within 3years	4	2.3
Pap smear result		
AGUS	1	0.6
ASC-H	1	0.6
ASCUS	19	10.9
HSIL	1	0.5
LSIL	7	4.0
NILM	143	81.7
Repeat	3	1.7

Note

HSIL- High grade squamous intraepithelial lesion, LSIL- low grade squamous intraepithelial lesion, ASCUS- Atypical squamous cell of undetermined significance, AGUS – Atypical glandular cells of undetermined significance, ASC-H- Atypical squamous cells in which high grade cannot be excluded, NILM- Negative for intraepithelial malignancy

Table 3: Prevalence of HIV and other STIs among female sex workers in Jos, Nigeria, n=175.

STIs	Overall n (%)	95% CI
HIV	39 (22.3%)	16.7-29.1
<i>Ureaplasma urealyticum</i>	89 (50.9%)	42.3-57.1
<i>Ureaplasma parvum</i>	97 (55.4%)	51.2-60.3
<i>Mycoplasma hominis</i>	81(46.3%)	40.1-54.9
<i>Mycoplasma genitalium</i>	26 (14.9%)	10.3-20.9
<i>Chlamydia trachomatis</i>	21 (12.0%)	10.1-15.9
<i>Neisseria gonorrhoea</i>	34 (19.4%)	15.5-24.8
<i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i>	31 (17.7%)	11.7-22.8

Table 4: Predictors of HIV infection

Variable	Odds Ratio	p-value	95% CI
Ingestion of Alcohol			
Yes	1.16	0.69	0.56-1.94
No	ref		
Abuse of other Substances			
Yes	1.89	0.27	0.61-5.82
No	ref		
History of STI			
Yes	1.04	0.93	0.43-2.52
No	ref		
Having a nonpaying Partner			
Yes	1.85	0.09	0.52-2.31
No	ref		
Consistent and correct use of condom always			
Yes	0.73	0.39	0.35-1.50
No	ref		
Age at Coitarche			
< 18years	1.09	0.81	0.52-2.31
≥ 18years	ref		
<i>Ureaplasma Urealyticum</i> infection			
Positive	1.01	0.99	0.49-2.05
Negative	ref		
<i>Mycoplasma hominis</i> infection			
Positive	1.28	0.50	0.63-2.61
Negative	ref		
<i>Mycoplasma genitalium</i> infection			
Positive	1.68	0.27	0.67-4.22
Negative	ref		
<i>Ureaplasma parvum</i> infection			
Positive	1.36	0.41	0.66-2.82
Negative	ref		
<i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i> infection			
Positive	1.01	0.98	0.39-2.56
Negative	ref		

Discussion

Human Papilloma Virus is one of the most prevalent sexually transmitted infections with associated morbidity and mortality. The study revealed a high prevalence of HIV and other STIs among BBFSW in Jos, Nigeria. Specifically, HIV prevalence was reported to be high, which aligns with previous findings reported in Jos,²⁷ and other regions in sub-Saharan Africa where sex workers were identified as a high-risk group for HIV infection.²⁸ Studies in Kenya²⁹ and Uganda³⁰ have reported similar HIV prevalence among sex workers, underscoring the persistent public health challenge posed by HIV in this demographic.

The prevalence of *Ureaplasma urealyticum* and *Ureaplasma parvum* was notably high occurring in greater than half of the participants, reflecting the widespread nature of these infections among sexually active populations. Studies in other parts of Nigeria and sub-Saharan Africa have reported varying prevalence, often influenced by factors such as sexual behaviour, condom use, and access to healthcare services.³¹ The high prevalence of these infections in the current study indicates the need for targeted interventions, including regular screening and treatment programmes. *Mycoplasma hominis* was detected in slightly less than half of the population while prevalence rates of *Neisseria gonorrhoea*, *Chlamydia trachomatis*, and *Trichomonas vaginalis* were also high. Prevalence of *mycoplasma* was more than one in ten. These findings are consistent with studies conducted in similar settings, where mycoplasma infections were commonly detected among sex workers.³² The low prevalence of *mycoplasma genitalium* compared to *mycoplasma hominis* suggests differential susceptibility or reporting issues that warrant further investigation.

Chlamydia trachomatis and *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* were detected in less than a third of the study participants. These two organisms are well-recognized STIs with significant public health implications. The prevalence observed in this study is comparable to that reported in Abuja and Lagos³³ and in other high-risk populations, such as sex workers in urban centers across Africa. These infections are often asymptomatic,

highlighting the importance of regular screening to prevent long-term complications and transmission. *Trichomonas vaginalis* is another common STI among the study participants. This prevalence was similar to findings from other studies in sub-Saharan Africa, where *Trichomonas vaginalis* was prevalent among women of reproductive age, particularly those engaged in sex work.³⁴

Factors associated with HIV infection in this study participants like inconsistent condom use, use of illicit drugs, ingestion of alcohol were similar to those reported in previous studies which is in line with the plausible explanation that HIV occurs in association with other high-risk behaviours.^{20,21,29,35} None of the STIs were statistically significantly associated with HIV infection. This was probably due to the relatively small sample size in this study. Being a cross-sectional study, we could not assess temporal relationship between STIs and other risk factors. There might be recall bias as some of the questions asked were based on self-report or recall. The study reported the prevalence of STIs among hard-to-reach population (BBFSW) using highly sensitive molecular methods in this environment. The study also assessed factors associated with HIV infection including association with other STIs. Another strength is that it has added to data on female sex workers and provided data that can be built on and referenced in subsequent studies.

Conclusion

The high prevalence of HIV and other STIs among BBFSW in Jos, Nigeria underscores the urgent need for comprehensive sexual health programmes targeting this population. Such programmes should include regular screening, treatment, education on safe sex practices, and access to preventive measures such as condoms and vaccines. Future research should focus on longitudinal studies to understand the dynamics of STI transmission and the effectiveness of intervention strategies. Additionally, qualitative studies exploring the behavioural and social factors influencing STI prevalence among sex workers could provide valuable insights for designing targeted interventions.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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